

The Important Role of Philosophy for Children (P4C)

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Abstract

The aim of this paper is to introduce the importance of philosophy for children (P4C) and present the importance of stories for children's moral foundation. The research question is why philosophy for children and children's stories are still important as an intellectual and moral foundation for the children in society.¹ Tentative solution is to prove that philosophy for the children and stories can cultivate moral and intellectual understanding and attitudes because children can easily remember the characters in the stories and so, they can be guided in distinguishing between moral and immoral, that is between good and bad, right and wrong through the behaviours of the characters in stories.² Descriptive, analytic and evaluative methods will be used to achieve the aim of the research.³ The principle of analysis will be used.⁴ This paper will contribute to the understanding that philosophy for children can be used as a way of teaching the children about the moral and intellectual issues and lessons and cultivated the children's thinking skills.⁵

Key words: philosophy for children, moral foundation, moral lessons, thinking skills

Introduction

The aim of philosophy for children is to develop the ability to go beyond the information given and to engage with texts not just in terms of their literal meaning but at an analytic and conceptual level. Children should be encouraged thinking for themselves and giving them the means to think critically, creatively and to solve problems. How to encourage independent thinking and cooperative learning are key questions for children at any age. Philosophy holds one possible answer for rather than being told what to think, through philosophy children encounter at first hand a community of enquiry, in which children are exposed to and internalize the skills and habits of higher order thinking.

Confucius said that if one learns from others but does not think, one will be bewildered. If, on the other hand, one thinks but does not learn from others, one will be in peril. The lesson is a literacy hour with a difference, for it has been given over to 'philosophy for children', an approach aimed at developing not just literacy, but a thinking. To develop the children's thinking skills, stories for children can be used as a tool. Not only listening stories but also creating own stories the children themselves may improve the analytic and conceptual skills.

Moreover, stories are very important in building moral character for children. People use stories as messages for children because the stories can deliver moral lessons and knowledge to children. The stories can be seen as social and cultural tools that proclaim humans as cultural beings, who share their experiences through stories.

As regards with children's stories, children can learn about the nature of animals and environmental situations and there are good opportunities to summarize human characteristics. Children's stories might be one of the effective ways to introduce values to young children and make children exercise their reasoning. Through examples of the stories they are able to reflect

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¹ Research Problem

² Research Finding

³ Research Problem

⁴ Research Principle

⁵ Contribution

on their lives. Children's stories are good way of developing a sense of morality and knowledge of children.

In the Chapter1, the characteristics of P4C (Philosophy for Children), Philosophy and thinking skills, Socratic Method and Children, and Pragmatic Method and children will be discussed and in the Chapter 2, it will explain the relation of Children and Stories, Children's Stories and Morality, Children's Stories and Education and the Usefulness of Digital Storytelling.

1. The Characteristics of Philosophy for Children (P4c)

Philosophy for Children (P4C) is an enquiry based pedagogy, where students take the lead and the teaching style is facilitative. Its aim is to drive questioning, reasoning and independent learning skills. Philosophy for Children(P4C) was the title Professor Matthew Lipman gave to his project of using the discipline of philosophy as resource to help children become more intellectually energetic, curious, critical, creative and reasonable. It is based on the principle that children should be given the opportunity to ask and openly discuss questions which are of relevance and importance to them. The skills the children learn through Philosophy for Children are life skills that have a positive impact across all areas of the curriculum as well as personally and socially.

Philosophy for Children promotes high expectations and children are encouraged to give reasons and explanations for their answers. Although it is both welcome and necessary that different opinions are expressed in a philosophical enquiry. This is done in a supportive, non-confrontational way, where the aim is to explore together, as a community, issues arising from a question and to try to draw some conclusions. In this way, P4C helps children to listen to, take account of, and respectfully but critically challenge other points of view. They learn to formulate reasoned arguments and to articulate their opinions to others. Philosophy calls on imagination and reasoning and puts these capacities to work exploring values, assumptions and vital concepts like justice, truth and knowledge.

Philosophy for Children promotes a forum for open dialogue in which participants are not content to exchange ideas and opinions as if they were bits of information. Instead they ask questions, sift arguments and explore alternatives.

1.1. Philosophy for children (P4C) and thinking skills

Among the thinking skills that philosophy for children aims to foster are just those skills which are namely information processing, enquiry, reasoning, creative thinking and evaluation. Philosophy for children provides opportunities for developing:

Information-processing skills through reading, discussion and writing to make meaning from the texts they read, identifying what they do and do not understand, reflecting on what they read and discuss, and interpreting information to show they understand relevant concepts and ideas.

Enquiry skills through reading, discussion and writing to ask relevant questions, pose problems, engage in a process of investigation and find possible solutions and open new areas of enquiry.

Reasoning skills through reading, discussion and writing to draw inferences and make deductions, give reasons for opinions, use precise language to explain what they think, and make judgments and decisions informed by reasons and/or evidence.

Creative thinking skills through reading, discussion and writing generate and be playful with ideas, suggest possible hypotheses, apply imagination to their thinking, and to look for alternative explanations and ideas.

Evaluation skills through reading, discussion and writing to apply their own judgments to contestable issues, develop criteria for judging the value of ideas, evaluate the ideas and contributions of others, and practice being self critical and self correcting.

These skills include the higher order thinking skills identified in many taxonomies of thinking skills. But skills alone are not enough, what must be added to these to make them effective are the dispositions to use the skills to make a difference. These involve two sets of dispositions or attitudes which philosophy for children aims to foster. Both derive from the dialogical nature of the process, developing individual skills through co-operative activity. It might call these aspects 'caring', 'collaborative' or 'connected' thinking. It is caring in the sense of taking responsibility for one's own thinking, and collaborative in the sense of being open to and connecting with what others think. Co-operative dispositions involve learning to collaborate and cooperate with others in a community of enquiry, building self esteem, empathy and respect towards others. Philosophy for children integrates all these aspects of thinking into one process. There are many philosophical methods which enhance the thinking skills of children. Among them, the Socratic Method and Pragmatic Method can be applied for Philosophy for Children (P4C).

1.2. The Socratic Method and Children

According to Plato the ancient Greek philosopher Socrates believed that "the unexamined life is not worth living". The 'examined life' on the other hand which necessitates development of the capacity for creative and critical reflection enables individuals to interrogate 'received' beliefs and values and break free from prejudicial, egocentric and impulsive habits of thought. In the Socratic view the search for truth is both a moral and rational enterprise. The Socratic Method is defined as an inductive process of "persistent and thorough questioning" enabling movement from specific examples of whatever is the case (e.g. justice) to tentative generalizations. Socrates believed that teaching is the art of asking questions.

P4C facilitators employ Socratic questioning to encourage pupils "to seek clarification, reasons and evidence, explore alternative views, test implications and consequences and ask questions about the question" and in doing so they model the habits of multidimensional thinking.

1.3. Pragmatic Philosophy and Children

The ideas of Charles Sanders Peirce and John Dewey can be clearly traced within the principles and practice of philosophy for children. Pragmatic philosophy rejects the Platonic notion of absolute truth in favour of an understanding of knowledge as a useful tool for "making our way in the world". Fallibilism, an understanding that human perception and methods of enquiry are prone to error, is inherent in a pragmatic view of knowledge. Peirce believed that scientific knowledge is tentative at best and the product of human contrivance embedded in practical judgments of a community of fallible enquirers.

Furthermore, Peirce asserted that progress towards more comprehensive understanding could only be achieved through participation in a community of self-corrective enquiry. Likewise, P4C does not regard knowledge claims as representations of the world 'as it really

is' but rather as a basis for action; the purpose of participation in a community of self-corrective enquiry is "to discover the consequences in lived experience, of employing our beliefs". Therefore, fallibilism and self-correction are fundamental aspects of the principles and practice of philosophy for children. Under a banking concept of education framework knowledge is fixed, certain and indisputable and notions of fallibility and self-correction are irrelevant.

John Dewey believed that human intelligence evolved through active problem-solving and that education should provide plenty of opportunities for engaging pupils in such creative activity. Dewey regarded education as enquiry and criticised the education system for being far too concerned with the transmission of knowledge and not concerned enough about the process of knowledge construction. Dewey argued that an education system which prevents opportunities for student enquiry was inherently undemocratic. It fails to teach the skills and dispositions necessary to enable full participation in the democratic process asserted that the community of philosophical enquiry represents:

"His social dimension of democracy in practice, for it both paves the way for the implementation of such practice and is emblematic of what such practice has the potential to become".¹

Dewey believed that education should be reconstructed along the lines of scientific enquiry. Based on his observations of human problem-solving, he developed a pattern of reflective thinking.

For children, they have no chance to experience the real life problems. But the stories help the children think about problem-solving. Children's stories are not only for entertainment purposes, but also to teach lessons, the world, Nature, people, animals and most significantly about how to behave well through simple moral lessons. Therefore, telling story is often considered to be a crucial aspect of humanity. Human beings have a natural ability to use verbal communication to teach, explain, and entertain, which is why telling story to the children is so prevalent in everyday life.

2. The Important Role of Stories for Children

The society humans live in today could not exist without the influence from past generations because human beings hand down lessons and knowledge from one generation to the next. Humans pride themselves on leaving a heritage of knowledge for their descendants to utilize. The tradition of telling story to the children facilitates this transfer of knowledge. As a result, storytelling remains to this day the single most important tradition humans participate in. The most important reason for this being that every story contains a lesson to instruct the children. Stories teach them to love, to forgive others, to be just and to strive for better in life. The greatest stories ever told function as a reflection on the world humans live in and of both the goodness and evil present in the world.

A Story has numerous important effects on daily lives. It has been one of the most effective sources of inspiration known to children. Storytelling acts as a fantastic teaching tool, imparting lessons of life to individuals of the children. The value of story holds as a source of inspiration and as a teaching tool makes it the most important tradition mankind possesses.

2.1. Children and Stories

Children are important for society because the development of society depends upon whether the children are well cultivated or not. Early childhood is a phrase often used to describe the period of a child's life before the age of five. It is the most rapid period of development in a human life and is critical to a child's cognitive, social, emotional, and physical development.

A child's environment during their early years has serious effects on the course of their adolescence and life course. What happens during the early years is of crucial importance for every child's development. It is a period of great opportunity, but also of vulnerability. When the quality of support, stimulation, and nurture is deficient, child development is seriously affected. Good nutrition, health, consistent loving care, and encouragement to learn in the early years of life help children to do better at school, be healthier, succeed in the working world, and participate more in society. Similarly, the mental and moral development of the children should be cared by telling moral stories since childhood.

It may convince that telling story to the children is a powerful method, and there are several reasons to that. One important aspect is that telling stories is a natural process and whenever people communicate, they tell stories. Stories are much easier to remember than facts and figures. Stories speak for themselves, and each learner can get out of it whatever is relevant to them and links to their personal experiences and needs. This is one reason why it makes a lot of sense to use story for purposes of the children's moral development.

2.2. Children's Stories and Morality

Stories play an important role in all societies and stories are often a vehicle for transmission of morals and values. The use of stories can be valuable in the teaching of morals and supports moral development of the children through the characters of the stories. Josepha Sherman said that

“Storytelling provides other growth opportunities, as stories help listeners to see through another's eyes and to share the protagonist's feelings of anger, fear, or love—all from a safe place. The Austrian-born American writer and child psychologist Bruno Bettelheim explained that stories are important to children because battling difficulties through story can help them face real-life troubles. Stories provide role models who show us how to face demons and overcome adversity.”ⁱⁱ

Stories have the potential to fulfill the goal of stimulating the moral imagination as stories have the power to evoke empathy in children. Stories provide concrete examples of values in action that listeners can relate to more meaningfully than they would to abstract communication of moral principles. In fact storytellers can manipulate stories to encourage empathy to one character over another, depending on the context or the moral lessons.

The story is a medium that stimulates the moral imagination, provides concrete details that allow for the recognition of moral issues. Moreover, it cultivates analytical skills through the practice of problem solving, elicits a sense of moral obligation through empathy and emotion, and reduces moral disagreement and ambiguity by normalizing social values. To better understand the way these functions take place, it should be considered what it is that makes storytelling effective in the transmission of morals and children build moral characters from reading or hearing moral stories.

Story has long been used as a way of transmitting morals from generation to generation. It has been tested by time and scientific inquiry and has been shown to fulfill a variety of functions toward that goal. Stories can entertain the children and educate them. Perhaps part of the success of storytelling to the children as a means of moral education lies in the inherency of both storytelling and morals to human nature.

2.3. Children's Stories and Education

Stories also can be used for educational purposes. Stories can help to develop a child's literary sensibilities, and listening to stories impresses a sense of story structure into a child's mind. Stories aid in stretching vocabulary, and children who are able to tell stories often gain advanced verbal ability and an increased sense of self-confidence.

Stories are one of the oldest educational tools through which cultures have passed down values and knowledge from one generation to the next. Story is a means of expressing experiences, emotions and ideas in different forms of transfer and dating back to ancient times. Despite all the modern innovations, the attraction of a story plays an important role, particularly, in the field of education.

Stories essentially are dramatic activities which encompass the non-verbal communication of body language, gestures and facial expressions. Therefore, the students absorb these elements mostly without their being an item of specific focus. And best of all, the students enjoy the activity.

It is important for children to make up stories, just as it is important for them to hear and respond to stories told by other people. When children create and tell a story in their own or a second language, the language becomes theirs. Oral language is an important tool for the cognitive growth of young children. So, Ahlberg and Howard discussed that

“In challenging and stimulating their child audience, these extend the invitation not only actively to engage and interact with literature as readers but also, in breaking down the barriers between the apparently definitive authority or “truth” of what is written and the myriad ways in which it may be told or interpreted, to become authors as well, with the courage and desire to tell their own stories.”ⁱⁱⁱ

With the increased use of the whole language approach to reading and writing, storytelling has taken on an important role. Students with experience in hearing and telling stories such as myths, legends, and folklore are eager to begin creating or writing their own stories. Stories are particularly important to children because they help children understand their world and share it with others. Children's hunger for stories is constant. Every time they enter the classroom, they enter with a need for stories. Using stories in the classroom, results in enhanced cultural awareness through the glimpses that stories afford into other people's worldview.

2.4. The Usefulness of Digital Storytelling

The term “digital storytelling” may not be familiar to all readers, over the last twenty years, an increasing number of educators, students and others around the world have created short movies by combining computer-based images, text, recorded audio narration, video clips and music in order to present information on various topics.

Digital storytelling combines the art of telling stories with a mixture of digital media, including text, pictures, recorded audio narration, music and video. These multimedia elements are blended together using computer software, to tell a story that usually revolves around a specific theme or topic and often contains a particular point of view.

Most digital stories are relatively, short with a length of between 2 and 10 minutes, and are saved in a digital format that can be viewed on a computer or other device capable of playing video files. In addition, digital stories are typically uploaded to the internet where they may be viewed through any popular web browser.

There are many different types of digital stories, but the author has proposed classifying the major types into the following three categories: personal narratives - stories that contain accounts of significant incidents in one's life; historical documentaries – stories that examine dramatic events that help us understand the past, and stories that inform or instruct the viewer on a particular concept or practice.

Digital storytelling has steadily grown in popularity and is currently being practiced in a myriad of locations, including schools, libraries, community centers, museums, medical and nursing schools, businesses and more. In educational settings, teachers and students from graduate school are creating digital stories on every topic imaginable, from art to zoology, and numerous content areas in between. Digital storytelling has also become a worldwide phenomenon, with practitioners from across the globe creating digital stories to integrate technology into the classroom, support language learning, and facilitate discussion.

Nowadays, in addition to asking students to watch digital stories created by others, digital storytelling can also be used to empower younger students when they use computer technology and multimedia resources to create their own stories that demonstrate their knowledge and understanding of educational themes and concepts.

Young people today are becoming more technologically savvy and they are increasingly engaged by activities that take place on a computer screen. Even very young students respond to and are motivated by creating computer-based materials, such as digital stories, that allow them to demonstrate their knowledge of the topics they are exploring in the classroom. One of the most important aspects of digital storytelling is that it can help make learning more relevant for students. Digital storytelling can encourage creativity as well as give students a voice as they use their stories to share their ideas and feelings with others.

Conclusion

It may argue that shifts in the political, economic, cultural and technological changes through the processes of globalization require a reconsideration of conventional educational paradigms. It may be recommended that the policy maker should make philosophical enquiry for a principle of basic education. Philosophy for Children (P4C) stresses the importance of building intellectual autonomy through the cultivation of multi-dimensional thinking. Moreover, it emphasizes a critical and reflective educational paradigm which advocates believe would better equip children and young people for the complexities of life in the 21st century.

Although P4C is mentioned in national educational policy discourse it is mostly viewed in instrumental terms. P4C continues to be an innovation operating on the margins of educational systems. However, successful implementation of P4C makes heavy demands on teachers, it is an uncertain, complex and risky activity which necessitates the adoption of a fallibilistic stance, an ability to relinquish a didactic role and assume a position of scholarly ignorance. Achieving this is no easy task in a climate where educational policy reinforces a

narrow banking concept of education and where children are credited with making intellectual progress, not when they begin to think for themselves, but when they begin to approximate national expectations based on narrow standard assessment tests. At the stage of childhood, to be able think themselves freely and to be able to cultivate their intellectual progress and to have the ability of problem-solving, stories which mean for children may be helpful and supportive for P4C (Philosophy for Children).

Children's stories provide children with the opportunity to respond and develop their own opinions. They can learn to evaluate and analyze, as well as summarize and hypothesize about the stories.

Moreover, children's stories help students develop emotional intelligence. Children's stories encourage them to think deeper about their own feelings and also encourage creativity. Children's stories may promote the development of children's internal imaginations because children are very impressionable during the formative years, and stories can help them develop into caring, intelligent, and friendly people.

Children's stories can promote social development by encouraging the children to accept other people and their differences, and may encourage them to become more open-minded to different types of families and understand that love is the most important thing in a family.

In the field of education, children's stories are valuable in both the school and at home, and valuable in providing an opportunity to respond to literature, as well as cultural knowledge, emotional intelligence and creativity, social and personality development, Exposing children to stories can contribute to the creation of responsible, successful, and caring individuals.

It may be concluded that telling stories to the children has been playing an important part for the moral foundations in the societies. The stories which differ in content and quality involve various elements such as entertainment, education, humanity, and results of actions, and other issues. In this way, stories give the children a collection of values, beliefs and attitudes certain already set patterns of behavior. These cultural values open the minds of the children to their immediate surroundings in particular and the world in general.

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